

Drug Utilization Study in Patients of Diabetes Attending Medicine OPD in A Tertiary Care Setup**Pradipta Das¹, Sughandha Garg², Paramita Pal (Bhattacharyya)³, Jaideep Bhaduri⁴**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Jagannath Gupta Institute of Medical Sciences and Hospital, Budge Budge, Kolkata, West Bengal, India²Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Jagannath Gupta Institute of Medical Sciences and Hospital, Budge Budge, Kolkata, West Bengal, India³Professor and Head of Department Pharmacology, Jagannath Gupta Institute of Medical Sciences and Hospital, Budge Budge, Kolkata, West Bengal, India⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmacology, Jagannath Gupta Institute of Medical Sciences and Hospital, Budge Budge, Kolkata, West Bengal, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Diabetes mellitus is a disease of inadequate control of blood levels of glucose. Diabetes mellitus is a metabolic disease, involving inappropriately elevated blood glucose levels.**Objectives:** To identify and assess drug utilization on patients suffering from diabetes mellitus in a tertiary care setup. To analyze the influence of various modifiable and non-modifiable factors on the effects of drugs prescribed to the patients.**Methods:** A Retrospective and Observational study was conducted at Jagannath Gupta Institute of Medical Sciences and Hospital, Budge Budge, Kolkata, West Bengal, India by a group of 6 students of batch 2020-21. A total of 160 responses were generated from past six months of hospital records. All adult patients (≥ 18 years) diagnosed and willing to give informed consent to participate in the study, were enrolled. The study was approved by Institutional Ethics Committee. The data was computed using IBM Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 24 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY) and results were expressed as counts and percentages.**Results:** Out of 135 DM patient's enrolled, male population (56.30%) and females (43.70%). Comparison out of 135 responses, comorbidities of diabetes patients had Hypertension 77 (57%) at higher rate than others. Obesity 8 (5.9%), Dyslipidemia 75 (55.6%), and others 52 (38.5%).**Conclusion:** After compiling the data it was seen that most common oral medication used was metformin. Hypertension and Dyslipidemia prevailed as the most common comorbidities. There was predominant family history of Type 2 DM in 59.9% of cases. Most common observed HbA1c level was found to be ranging between 7.0 to 8.0.**Keywords:** Diabetes mellitus, Dyslipidemia, Hypertension, Obesity.

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Introduction

The most prevalent metabolic illness impacting people worldwide is diabetes mellitus (DM). Globally, 285 million people had diabetes in 2010, and by 2030, it's predicted that over 438 million people will have the disease [1]. India's diabetes population is predicted to grow from approximately 69.2 million in 2015 to 123.5 million in 2040 [2]. Diabetes has two main complications: acute problems and chronic problems. Diabetes drugs can cause unusually low blood sugar or dangerously increased blood sugar as acute problems. Chronic complications are related to disorders of both small and large blood vessels, which can harm the kidneys, heart, nerves, eyes, and nerves [3]. To en-

hance quality of life, diabetes mellitus (DM) must be treated appropriately as it can lead to both morbidity and mortality. Type 2 diabetes is pharmacologically managed with insulin and a variety of oral antidiabetic medications (OADs). Sulfonylureas, biguanides, and more recent medications like alpha glucosidase inhibitors, thiazolidinediones, meglitinides, and the recently developed glucagon-like peptide analogs, dipeptidyl peptidase inhibitors, and sodium glucose co-transport 2 (SGLT-2) inhibitor are the OADs used to treat type 2 diabetes [4]. Drug therapy has been rationalized and standardized by the WHO and a number of other international and national medical agencies [5]. The crea-

tion of an essential drug lists—a distinct list for each nation—was one initiative. The names and dosage forms of all medications that should always be available to patients in that nation are listed in the national essential list [6]. To guarantee that medications are reasonable and easily accessible in accordance with worldwide recommendations, clinicians are urged to prescribe medications from the national essential medicine list.

The National Essential List of India for 2015 lists metformin and glimepiride as the only oral hypoglycemics approved for the treatment of diabetes mellitus [7].

The objective of the study was to identify and assess drug utilization on patients suffering from diabetes mellitus in a tertiary care setup. To analyze the influence of various modifiable and non-modifiable factors on the effects of drugs prescribed to the patients.

Methods

A Retrospective and Observational study was conducted at Jagannath Gupta Institute of Medical Sciences and Hospital, India by a group of 6 students of batch 2020-21. A total of 160 responses were generated from past six months of hospital records.

Inclusion Criteria: All adult patients (≥ 18 years) diagnosed with type 2DM and willing to give informed consent to participate in the study was enrolled.

Exclusion Criteria : Pregnant women and patients declining to give informed consent would be excluded from the study.

Study Population: Patient's admitted in last 6 months of Jagannath Gupta Institute of Medical Sciences and Hospital, Budge Budge, Kolkata, West Bengal, India.

Study tools (i) Questionnaire: An anonymous, confidential, self-administered structured questionnaire was used which included their age, gender, family history, Tobacco intake or alcohol use was taken as a part of relevant history (ii) Anthropometric measurements:-Their height and weight were measured by height tape and weighing machine respectively. (iii) Blood pressure: Taken from patient's file, Measured by sphygmomanometer and stethoscope(iv)Drugs taken by the patient is also noted down.

Purpose of Study: The purpose of research is to inform and is based on collected and analyzed data. This exploration occurs systematically, where it is either tested or investigated to add to a body of knowledge. It helps us in understanding the effect of various drugs on a single disease which is more advantageous to the patients. Helps us understand the prognosis of the patients under treatment.

Statistical Analysis: The descriptive data were reported in percentages for categorical variables and mean(\pm)SD for continuous variables.

All statistical calculations were done using IBM Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 24 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY).

Results

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of study population

SN	Characteristics		N=135	Percentage
1	Age (years)	30-40	4	2.97%
		41-50	22	16.30%
		51-60	40	29.62%
		61-70	60	44.45%
		71-80	9	6.66%
2	Gender	Male	76	56.30%
		Female	59	43.70%
3	Family history			59.9%
4	HbA1C			7.0 to 8.0

Most of the patients diagnosed with type 2 DM were of the age group of 61-70 years (44.45%) followed by 51-60 years (29.62%) age groups. Male population (56.30%) had higher prevalence of type 2 DM than females (43.70%). There was predominant family history of Type 2 DM in 59.9% of cases. Most common observed HbA1c level was found to be ranging between 7.0 to 8.0, shown in Table 1.

Table 2: Comorbidities of Diabetes Patents

SN	Comorbidities	Percentage
1	Hypertension	77 (57%)
2	Obesity	8 (5.9%)
3	Dyslipidemia	75 (55.6%)
4	others	52 (38.5%),

Figure 1: Comorbidities of Diabetes Patents

Comparison out of 135 responses, comorbidities of diabetes patents had Hypertension 77 (57%) at higher rate than others. Obesity 8 (5.9%), Dyslipidemia 75 (55.6%), and others 52 (38.5%), shown in Table 2 and Figure 1.

Table 3: Prescribing frequency of different antidiabetic drugs in study population

SN	Drug	Percentage
1	Metformin (Biguanide)	86 (62.3%)
2	Glimepiride (sulfonylureas)	36 (26.1%)
3	Insulin	16 (11.6%)

Figure 2: Number of drugs prescribed per prescription from NLEM

Out of 138 responses, Metformin was used 86 (62.3%) as highest rate at compared to other drugs, Glimepiride utilized 36 (26.1%) and Insulin used 16 (11.6%). After compiling the data it was seen that most common oral medication used was metformin, shown in Table 3 and Figure 2.

Discussion

Prescription pattern studies serve as a research tool for clinical pharmacology as well as a source of suggestive data for epidemiology. Drug use or prescription trend analysis is a component of medical audit. Monitoring, evaluating, and making any necessary adjustments to prescription practices is the aim of medical audit, which aims to provide reasonable and cost-effective pharmacotherapy. Con-

ducting studies on the application of anti-diabetic drugs is essential for enhancing medicine therapy and drug administration [8]. In the current study, type 2 diabetes Male population (56.30%) had higher prevalence of type 2 DM than females (43.70%). Table 1 show that men outnumbered women, which is consistent with findings from earlier surveys carried out in India [9-11].

The majority of the patients in the current study had mean HbA1c values between 7.0 and 8.0, indicating poor glycemic control. Haghghatpanah et al.'s investigation yielded similar results, with a mean HbA1c of 8.6 ± 2.2 . It implies that the anti-diabetic medication that the study population was given was subpar. [2].

Based on Table 3, Figure 2, the most often prescribed class of OADs in the current study is Metformin (Biguanide), with 86 (62.3%), followed by Glimeperide (sulfonylureas) with 36 (26.1%). Prior research yielded comparable findings. However, a small number of studies found that biguanides (20%) and sulfonylureas (33%) are the two most often given medication classes. [3]

This indicates that biguanides and sulfonylureas remain the preferred treatments for diabetic mellitus among most doctors. A small number of studies also revealed that prescriptions for more recent pharmacological classes, such as glitazones (1.1%), dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP-4) inhibitors (4%), and α -glucosidase inhibitors (4.8%), were also written. The government tertiary care hospital's irregular supply of certain medicine types may be the cause. According to a research by Venkateswaramurthy et al., glimepiride is the most often given OAD, with metformin coming in second at 42.25 percent [12].

For those with type 2 diabetes who are overweight or obese, metformin is the recommended medication. Metformin plays a significant role in the pathophysiology of type 2 diabetes because it is a peripheral insulin sensitizer and improves insulin resistance [13]. As a result, the majority of individuals with type 2 diabetes mellitus were reported to use metformin as their first medication of choice. Metformin has positive benefits on a number of cardiovascular risk factors and does not encourage weight gain.

The strong glucose-lowering efficacy of a number of novel OADs, such as injectable DPP-4 inhibitors and glucagon-like peptide-1 agonists, is a benefit. These drugs enable long-term weight loss with a minimal risk of hypoglycemia.

Therefore, we advise doctors to prescribe more recent OADs in combination.

Limitations

One of the study's limitations was that the data was gathered at a specific period. Therefore, no documentation of further care was made. The study only looked at a small number of patients over a brief period of time. Therefore, additional research involving a sizable patient population at several sites is required to validate the study's findings.

Conclusion:

Continuous monitoring is necessary to effectively manage a chronic condition like diabetes mellitus. Additionally, the patients have to take an active part in it. Physicians' continual education to stay up to date on new advancements would also be beneficial for the rational administration of antidiabetic drugs and the effective management of diabetes mellitus. Metformin was shown to be the most often utilized oral drug once the data was compiled.

Hypertension and Dyslipidemia prevailed as the most common comorbidities. There was predominant family history of Type 2 DM in 59.9% of cases. Most common observed HbA1c level was found to be ranging between 7.0 to 8.0.

Ethical approval: The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee

References:

1. Rani J, Reddy S. Prescribing pattern of antidiabetic drugs in urban population of Hyderabad. *Natl J Physiol Pharm Pharmacol.* 2015; 5:5-9.
2. Haghghatpanah M, Thunga G, Jha A, Malayasamy S. Study on prescribing pattern of anti-diabetic drugs among type 2 diabetes Patients with complication in south indian teaching hospital. *Asian J Pharm Clin Res.* 2016; 9: 194-7.
3. Vengurlekar S, Shukla P, Patidar P, Bafna R, Jain S. Prescribing pattern of antidiabetic drugs in indore city hospital. *Indian J Pharm Sci.* 2008; 70(5):637-40.
4. Akila L, Sandozi T, Geetha Devi AK, Kumar JS, Balasubramanian A, Jamuna Rani R. Drug utilization study of oral anti-diabetic drugs at a tertiary care (SRM Medical College) hospital in Chennai. *Int J Med Res.* 2011; 1:177-82.
5. WHO | Rational use of medicines [Internet]. WHO. Available from: http://www.who.int/medicines/areas/rational_use/en/
6. WHO | Essential medicines [Internet]. WHO. Available from: http://www.who.int/topics/essential_medicines/en/
7. National List of Essential Medicines (NLEM) 2015 - India [Internet]. Available from: http://apps.who.int/medicine_docs/en/m/abstract/Js23088en/
8. Nyamagoud SB, Swamy AH, Kangrali B. Drug Utilization Evaluation of Antidiabetic Drugs in a Tertiary Care Teaching Hospital: Analysis from a Randomized Controlled Study. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Investigation.* 2023 Jul 1; 13(3).
9. Abdi SA, Churi S, Kumar YS. Study of drug utilization pattern of antihyperglycemic agents in a South Indian tertiary care teaching hospital. *Indian J Pharmacol.* 2012; 44(2):210-4.
10. Ramesh R, Kumar SV, Gopinath S, Gavaskar B, Gandhiji G. Diabetic knowledge of rural community and drug utilization pattern in a tertiary care hospital. *Int J Pharm Life Sci* 2011; 2(1):531-5.
11. Sivasankari V, Manivannan E, Priyadarsini SP. Drug utilization pattern of antidiabetic drugs in a rural area of Tamil Nadu, South India - A prospective, observational study. *Int J Pharm Biol Sci.* 2013; 4(1):514-9.
12. Venkateswaramurthy N, Shajeem S, Sambathkumar R. Prescribing pattern of antidiabetic

- drugs in type-2 diabetic patients. Int J Pharm Sci Res. 2016; 7:4550-55.
13. Sultana G, Kapur P, Aqil M, Alam MS, Pillai KK. Drug utilization of oral hypoglycemic

agents in a university teaching hospital in India. J Clin Pharm Ther. 2010; 35(3):267-77.